

The support affects the catalytic conversion in thymol hydrogenation reaction

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogenation of the aromatic ring in phenolic compounds is an important reaction in industry and in the synthesis of fine chemicals. Pd-supported catalysts have proved to be highly active and efficient in deep hydrogenation of aromatic ring. Previous studies confirmed that the acidity and topology properties of the support play an important role in the efficient transformation of the phenolic reactant. In this study, we have investigated the effect of these two parameters by designing advanced layered MFI and MWW zeolites. To understand the effect of acidity, we compared the catalytic performance of a series of Pd/MFI catalysts that significantly differed in the acidity of the support. Then, we compared the catalytic results from Pd on aluminosilicate MFI and Pd/MCM-56 to see the effect of the support's topology. Thymol was used as a model phenolic reactant, and the results confirmed that not only the Pd on non-acidic MFI support was inactive (conversions below 25 %), but also the acidity of the MFI support led to higher thymol conversion (47 %), while more weak acid centers and silanol groups in dealuminated MFI topped up the outcome (100 % conversion). Data also showed that between two aluminosilicate supports, the MWW outperformed MFI (100 % vs. 47 %), due to its topology and morphology for better accommodating thymol and interacting with it.

1. Introduction

Catalytic hydrogenation is widely applied in large-scale industry and in fine chemistry. This reaction is performed for selective reduction of functional groups, containing C=C, C=O, C=N, and other unsaturated bonds in various types of molecules in order to get valuable products or to remove undesired functionality [1]. Among possible hydrogenation reactions, saturation of aromatic ring is one of the most challenging processes, which requires relatively harsh conditions (elevated temperatures and hydrogen pressures of several tens of bars) and highly active catalysts, be it homogeneous or heterogeneous. Considering heterogeneous materials more attractive in practice, these catalysts are usually represented by mixed non-noble [2] and single component noble metal [3] species deposited on carbonaceous or oxidic supports, and in particular on zeolites.

Metal species are the most obvious objectives for optimization, both in terms of chemical composition and in terms of particle size. Therefore, numerous theoretical and experimental studies as well as Reviews can

be found on this topic [4–6]. Metal species can be deposited on the supports in the form of isolated metal atoms, metal clusters, and nanoparticles (NPs) influencing the activity of the resultant supported catalyst [7], which is the conventional matter of investigation. However, the support can also play an important role in the overall performance of the catalyst, for example by adsorbing the aromatic reactant near the metallic sites or by providing shape selectivity to a desired product [8, 9]. Even though a literature review suggests that the properties of the support affect the catalytic performance, the role of these properties in hydrogenation reactions is not always clear, because it is difficult to control the single characteristic of a solid material without influencing the rest of its parameters. We aim to fill the gap in this study by using hydrogenation of thymol as the model reaction catalyzed by Pd NPs deposited on layered zeolites.

Over the last decade, layered zeolites of different structural types and interlayer architecture were designed. This diversity together with high uniformity and high accessibility of external surface make layered zeolites attractive objects for investigation of the role of support in

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hydrogenation reactions. Lamellar MFI and MWW (MCM-56) are the most studied representatives of layered zeolites with well-established synthesis protocols [10]. Both lamellar MFI and MWW are composed of thin disorderly stacked layers with very weak interlayer connectivity with 10-ring channels in the layers, while MWW has additional 12-ring cups exposed to the exterior surface of its layers [11,12].

The chemical composition, acidity, defects, and topology are the key descriptors of the support that can affect the outcome of the hydrogenation reaction [9,13,14]. A change in the nature of the support's surface can influence the support-reactant interaction [15], while changing the topology of the support with the same metal can affect the stabilization of the reaction intermediates and regioselectivity [8,16–18]. In this study, we custom-designed a series of advanced layered supports based on MFI and MWW structures for loading of Pd NPs and further investigation of the role of the key descriptors of the support in hydrogenation of thymol – as a representative of the substituted aromatic compounds – with a methodical approach.

However, understanding the role of the support properties in the reaction should not be interfered by the difference in the characteristics of deposited metal species, therefore the metal loading and the nanoparticle size were kept almost constant (otherwise the difference is considered in more details). To analyze the effect of the acidity of the support, we made pair-wise comparisons between Pd/MFI_(lam,Si) prepared by Pd loading on purely siliceous layered zeolite and Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) synthesized using its aluminosilicate analogue (Fig. 1). The latter support was further treated by partial dealumination to generate extra silanols on the zeolite surface, enabling the comparison of the resulting deficient Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl) with the parent intact material Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si). To see how the topology of the support affects the catalysis, we compared the results from the Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) and Pd/MCM-56. Finally, Pd/MCM-56 was tested under different reaction conditions by varying the temperature, hydrogen pressure, and the amount of the catalyst to reveal the influence of these variables. The conclusions made here can give insight into how the support might affect the outcome of hydrogenation reactions in the case of phenolic reactants.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Synthesis of the supports and loading of Pd nanoparticles

The purely siliceous layered MFI, aluminosilicate layered MFI, dealuminated layered MFI, layered aluminosilicate MCM-56 and MCM-22 were synthesized in the following way. Conventional MFI was purchased from Zeolyst International and was used as a reference support in comparisons. Pd/C was purchased from STREM CHEMICALS Inc. and was used as a reference catalyst in comparisons. Pd nanoparticles were loaded on the supports by wet impregnation method.

2.1.1. Synthesis of purely siliceous layered MFI (MFI_(lam,Si))

Purely siliceous layered MFI support was synthesized using a similar procedure as to how it is described in Ref. [11]. In a typical synthesis of

the layered MFI_(Si), 0.01 mol of tetraethylorthosilicate (for synthesis, Merck) was added to 10.8 mL of an aqueous solution containing 0.0007 mol of C_{18,6,6}(OH)₂. The mixture was stirred for about 10 min at room temperature until it became a homogeneous sol. The resultant mixture was cooled in an ice bath and 0.003 mol of n-butyl alcohol (99.9 %, Merck) was added dropwise. The resultant gel was further homogenized at 60 °C for 3 h under stirring. The molar composition of the final gel mixture was 100SiO₂:7C_{18,6,6}(OH)₂:6000H₂O:30n-butyl alcohol. The resultant gel was transferred to a Teflon-lined autoclave and was hydrothermally crystallized at 140 °C under tumbling conditions. After a 10-day hydrothermal treatment, the zeolite product was filtered, washed with deionized water, and dried. The as-synthesized zeolite was calcined at 550 °C for 3 h under airflow.

2.1.2. Synthesis of aluminosilicate layered MFI (MFI_(lam,Al-Si))

Aluminosilicate layered MFI and the di-quaternary ammonium type surfactant (C₂₂H₄₅-N⁺(CH₃)₂-C₆H₁₂-N⁺(CH₃)₂-C₆H₁₃, here denoted as C₂₂₋₆₋₆) were synthesized following the procedures described in Ref. [19]. The hydroxide form of the surfactant was prepared through the anion exchange of C₂₂₋₆₋₆Br₂. This surfactant was mixed with tetraethylorthosilicate (for synthesis, Merck), aluminum sulfate (99.99 %, Thermo Scientific), H₂SO₄ (96 %, Lachner) and deionized water to give a molar composition of 1Al₂O₃:100SiO₂:15C₂₂₋₆₋₆(OH)₂:3H₂SO₄:6000H₂O. This mixture was heated to 150 °C for 11 days in an autoclave with tumbling to obtain the layered MFI_(Al-Si) support.

2.1.3. Dealumination of layered aluminosilicate MFI to get dealuminated MFI (MFI_(lam,deAl))

Dealumination (deAl) was performed on MFI_(lam,Al-Si) via the acid treatment with 0.5 M solution of HNO₃ (68 %, VWR) at 100 °C under reflux using 1 g zeolite per 25 mL solution for 2 h. Afterwards, the flask was cooled down and the solid product was recovered by centrifugation, washed with deionized water until neutral pH was reached, and finally it was dried overnight at 75 °C.

2.1.4. Synthesis of layered aluminosilicate MCM-56

Layered MCM-56 was prepared under hydrothermal conditions based on the procedure described in Ref. [12]. The synthesis gel was prepared by mixing deionized water, 50 % NaOH (99.2 %, VWR) solution, sodium aluminate (50–56 wt% Al₂O₃, 40–45 wt% Na₂O, Riedel-de Haën), hexamethylenimine (denoted as HMI, 99 %, Sigma Aldrich), and Ultrasil VN3 (Sigma Aldrich) in the following molar ratios: Si/Al = 11.5, OH/Si = 0.21, HMI/Si = 0.35, H₂O/Si = 19.2. Crystallization proceeded in a Parr reactor at 143 °C for 33 h. The as-synthesized zeolite was calcined under a nitrogen flow at 482 °C for 3 h (with a temperature ramp of 1 °C/min), followed by heating to 540 °C (1 °C/min) for 8 h under airflow.

2.1.5. Synthesis of layered aluminosilicate MCM-22P

Layered aluminosilicate MCM-22P with theoretical Si/Al = 15 was prepared following the protocol in Ref. [20]. To synthesize MCM-22P,

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the types of supports selected for comparison.

114 g Ludox LS-30 (Sigma Aldrich), 5.62 g NaOH (99.2 %, VWR), 1.86 g sodium aluminate (50–56 wt% Al_2O_3 , 40–45 wt% Na_2O , Riedel-de Haën), 18.92 g HMI (99 %, Sigma Aldrich), and 200 g of deionized water was used. The mixture was stirred intensively until a homogeneous gel was formed. Then, it was transferred into a Teflon-lined stainless autoclave. The hydrothermal crystallization was done at 143 °C for 96 h under mechanical stirring. The synthesized MCM-22P zeolite was separated by filtration, washed with deionized water, and dried at 60 °C overnight. Afterwards, it was calcined at 480 °C for 3 h under a nitrogen flow, followed by a heating step at 540 °C for 6 h under airflow. The target MCM-22 support was obtained after calcination.

2.1.6. Conventional MFI support

Conventional (commercial) MFI zeolite (CBV 3024E) in the ammonium form with Si/Al ratio of 15 was purchased from Zeolyst International and was used as the support for loading of 1 wt% Pd NPs, denoted hereafter as Pd/MFI_(con).

2.1.7. Commercial Pd/C

Commercial Pd/C with 1 wt% Pd loading (CAS:7440-05-3) was purchased from STREM CHEMICALS Inc. and was used as a reference catalyst in the hydrogenation reaction of thymol.

2.1.8. Wet impregnation of Pd nanoparticles on the designed supports

Wet impregnation of 1 wt% Pd NPs on the MFI and MWW supports was done in the following way: 2.5 g of each zeolite was mixed with an appropriate amount of deionized water and 0.75 g of Pd precursor tetraaminepalladium(II) nitrate solution (10 wt% in H_2O , Sigma Aldrich) in a closable plastic bag. After adding the zeolite and the Pd solution into the bag, the bag was pressed by hands to make a homogeneous mixture. Then, deionized water was slowly added by a pipette to the Pd precursor. The amount of added deionized water was 1.6 mL in case of MFI_(Si), 1.1 mL for both MFI_(Al-Si) and MFI_(deAl), 2.5 mL for MFI_(con), 6.5 mL for MCM-56, and 10.5 mL for MCM-22. Then, the sample was pressed until a wet homogenous mixture was formed. The plastic bag was opened, put in the oven, and dried overnight at 75 °C. Finally, the bag was cut, and the Pd-supported catalyst was collected and dried at 75 °C for 6 more hours.

2.2. Characterization

2.2.1. PXRD

To confirm the topology of the catalysts, powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) analysis was performed on a D8 ADVANCE BRUKER diffractometer equipped with a LYNXEYE XE-T detector in the Bragg–Brentano geometry using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. Data were collected in 2θ range of 3–40° with 0.021° step size and 0.8 s time per step.

2.2.2. N_2 adsorption

To investigate the textural properties of the catalysts, N_2 adsorption analysis was performed on a Micromeritics 3Flex Surface Characterization Analyzer at –196 °C. Before the measurements, the samples were degassed on a Micromeritics Smart Vac Prep instrument under vacuum, starting at an ambient temperature up to 110 °C (1 °C/min) until the residual pressure of 13.3 Pa was achieved. After heating at 110 °C for 1 h, the temperature was increased to 250 °C with 1 °C/min ramp and remained there for 8 h. The BET area was evaluated using Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method. The t-plot method was used to evaluate the volume of micropores (V_{mic}) and the external surface area (S_{ext}) of the supports. The adsorbed amount of N_2 at the relative pressure of 0.95 is the total adsorption capacity (V_{tot}), and the mesopore volume (V_{meso}) is a subtraction of $V_{\text{tot}} - V_{\text{mic}}$.

2.2.3. SEM & TEM

To investigate the uniform distribution and the size range of the Pd NPs and to observe the layered structure of the supports, transmission

electron microscope (TEM) images of the catalysts were taken using JEOL NeoARM 200 F microscope equipped with a Schottky-type field emission gun operated at an accelerating voltage of at 200 kV. To investigate the morphology of the supports, SEM images of the catalysts were taken using a JEOL JSM-6380 LV Scanning Electron Microscope.

2.2.4. FTIR

To investigate the acidity of the supports, Fourier Transformed Infrared (FTIR) analysis of pyridine probe molecule adsorbed on the catalysts was performed using a NICOLET iS50 FT-IR spectrometer. The FTIR instrument was equipped with a deuterated triglycine sulfate (DTGS) detector. Prior to the measurement, the samples were pressed to form self-supporting wafers with a density of 10 mg/cm², followed by activation under vacuum at 450 °C for 4 h. Pyridine adsorption (partial pressure 3.5 Torr) was performed for 20 min at 150 °C. Desorption of the adsorbed pyridine was performed for 20 min at 150, 250, 350, and 450 °C, and the related spectra were collected. The total scan number was 64 and the spectral resolution was 4 cm⁻¹. To calculate the concentration of the Brønsted and Lewis acid sites, molar absorption coefficients were taken from the literature [21,22].

2.2.5. NMR

¹H MAS NMR and ²⁷Al MAS NMR experiments were performed on an 11.7 T Bruker AVANCE-III HD spectrometer using 2.5 mm rotors at a spinning frequency of 20 kHz (operating at a Larmor frequency of 500.5 MHz and 130.4 MHz, respectively). The ¹H single-pulse acquisition was employed with a pulse width of 1.9 μs for a $\pi/2$ -nutation angle, a recycle delay of 5 s, and 128 scans. The ²⁷Al single-pulse acquisition was employed with a pulse width of 0.7 μs, which corresponded to a $\pi/2$ -nutation in case of a selective central transition excitation, a recycle delay of 1 s, and 17000 to 32000 scans, without ¹H decoupling.

For a 2D ¹H-²⁷Al HETCOR experiment, the ¹H [20] D-HMQC pulse sequence with a SR4₁² dipolar recoupling was employed. Both ¹H (directly detected) and ²⁷Al spins were excited using rectangular pulses of 1.8 μs and 0.7 μs, respectively, while the SR4₁² recoupling sequence comprised sinc-shaped pulses of one quarter the rotor period (12.5 μs). The ¹H signal was acquired without decoupling in 22 rotor-synchronized time increments in the indirect dimension, with 1024–1280 scans at each step and a recycle delay of 3 s.

The chemical shift scales were referenced using the ¹³C spectrum of solid adamantane.

2.2.6. ICP-MS

To obtain the Si/Al ratio and the Pd percentage loaded on the supports, Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectroscopy (ICP-MS) was performed for the reduced catalysts on an Agilent 7900 ICP-MS. 50 mg of each catalyst was digested in 1.8 mL of HNO_3 (67–69 %, ANALPURE), 5.4 mL of HCl (34–37 %, ANALPURE), and 1.8 mL of HF (47–51 %, ANALPURE). Then, it was transferred into a closed Teflon vessel, placed in a Speedwave XPERT Berghof microwave, and heated at 210 °C (5 °C/min) for 25 min. After cooling down, the complexation of the surplus HF was done by adding 12 mL of H_3BO_3 ($\geq 99.5\%$, VWR). Further treatment in the microwave was performed at 190 °C (5 °C/min) for 10 min. Finally, the obtained cooled solutions were diluted for analysis.

2.3. Catalysis

Hydrogenation of thymol was done in PID Eng. and Tech. Micromeritics batch reactors of 70 mL volume. The reactors were connected to nitrogen and hydrogen gas inlets. Nitrogen was used for inertializing the reactor and the gas leak test. The reaction mixture was prepared from 1 g (6.7 mmol) of thymol ($\geq 98\%$, Alfa Aesar) in 40 mL of n-octane (98 %, Merck) as the solvent and 680 μL (3 mmol) of n-dodecane (for synthesis, Sigma Aldrich) as internal standard for gas chromatography (GC) analysis. The catalysts were reduced in a tubular oven prior to the reaction. The reduction procedure was as follows: 1 h inertializing the

catalyst with 50 mL/min flow of N₂ at room temperature, followed by increasing the temperature with a ramp of 10 °C/min to 350 °C while introducing H₂ at a 50 mL/min flow, and then an isothermal condition at 350 °C for 4h under a mixture of N₂ and H₂ with equal flow rates of 50 mL/min.

The reaction was done at 150 °C (or 100, 125, and 175 °C) by heating with a jacket, and the temperature was kept constant during reaction by automatic regulations of the heater. The hydrogen pressure was kept at 20 bars (or 10 and 50 bars) during the reaction by automatic injection of the gas. The catalyst amount in the reaction mixture was 100 mg unless for investigations of the effect of this parameter, when we also tested 25 and 50 mg catalyst. The samples of reaction mixture were taken manually over 5 h of reaction time.

An Agilent 8860 GC system with a low polarity HP-5 column (30 m × 0.32 mm × 0.25 μm) connected to a flame ionization detector (FID) was used for the analysis of the samples. A Thermo Scientific Trace 1310 GC system with a TG-5MS column (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm) connected to an ISQ LT Single Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (MS) was used to confirm the identity of the products. The standard chemical for menthone (97 %, Alfa Aesar) was used for confirmation of the identity of its related peak on the chromatogram, and the rest of the products (isomenthone, and cis- and trans-p-menthane) were identified from the intensity vs. mass/charge pattern given by GC-MS.

The conversion of thymol and the yield of the products were calculated from Eqs. (1) and (2):

$$X(\%) = [(n(\text{thymol})_0 - n(\text{thymol})_t) / n(\text{thymol})_0] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Y(\%) = [n(\text{product})_t / n(\text{thymol})_0] \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Where $n(\text{thymol})_0$ and $n(\text{thymol})_t$ are the amounts of thymol in the reaction mixture initially and at the specific time t based on the areas, and $n(\text{product})_t$ is the amount of the product i in the reaction mixture (based on its area) at the specific reaction time t .

3. Results and discussion

Layered zeolitic supports differing in acidity, surface deficiency, and topological properties were synthesized using the approaches described in Section 2.1. Then, wet impregnation method was used to load 1 wt % Pd in the form of NPs on all the supports. Since the control of structural, textural, and acidic parameters of the supports as well as the characteristics of the metal NPs were essential for the evaluation of properties-activity relationships, these properties are firstly discussed in Section 3.1, and later the correlation of the key support descriptors with catalysis is explained in Section 3.2.

3.1. Characterization

3.1.1. Topology of the catalysts

The PXRD patterns of the Pd/MFI_(lam,Si), Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si), and Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl) corresponded to the MFI topology (characteristic peaks at 7.9 and 8.8°; Fig. S1), as well as Pd/MFI_(con). The PXRD patterns of the MWW type zeolites (Pd/MCM-56 and Pd/MCM-22) were also in agreement with those in the literature, for which the characteristic peaks appeared at 7.2 and 8.1°; Fig. S1 [11,19,23]. The PXRD patterns confirmed that the catalysts with the target support topologies were successfully synthesized.

3.1.2. Textural properties of the catalysts

N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at -196 °C (Fig. 2) and the textural properties of the catalysts (Table 1) were in agreement with the characteristics of the corresponding materials.

Pd/MFI_(lam,Si) showed a combined type (I) + (IV) adsorption isotherm with an H3 hysteresis loop, which is typical for layered zeolites (Fig. 2). The H3 hysteresis is a result of the capillary condensation in the voids between 2D layers, which behaved like long narrow pores formed

Fig. 2. N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms (at -196 °C) of the reduced catalysts.

from non-rigid aggregates of MFI platelets [24]. The almost coinciding adsorption isotherms of Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) and Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl) were also type (I) + (IV), characteristic for hierarchical materials containing both micropores and mesopores (Fig. 2), but they had a different hysteresis from Pd/MFI_(lam,Si). The H4 hysteresis loop for pristine and dealuminated MFI supports is a result of the capillary condensation in the voids between 2D MFI layers, which behaved like slit-shaped pores [24]. Compared to these catalysts, Pd/MCM-56 and Pd/MCM-22 had an adsorption isotherm relatively close to a type (I), which is characteristic of microporous zeolites. The small hysteresis loop for the MCM-56 is less pronounced compared to those for lamellar MFI because of a more packed morphology of the MWW layers (explained later using microscopy images). This packed morphology created less voids (in terms of total void volume) in between the layers.

As expected, the Si/Al ratio increased from 22 to 30 after the dealumination of the MFI_(lam,Al-Si) support to MFI_(lam,deAl) (Table 1). The 1 % Pd content from ICP-MS analysis in all the samples corresponded to the theoretical Pd content considered during the impregnation process. The total BET area evaluated by nitrogen adsorption was in the range of 415–550 m²/g for the synthesized catalysts.

In addition to the similar adsorption behavior (Fig. 2), the external surface area (S_{ext}) in the layered MFI supports was comparable (220–251 m²/g, Table 1). However, the S_{ext} of MWW type supports were smaller than those of layered MFI (118 m²/g for MCM-56 and 93 m²/g for MCM-22). The smaller S_{ext} of MCM-22 compared to S_{ext} of MCM-56 is due to the condensed morphology of the MWW layers in MCM-22 compared to the house-of-cards morphology of the same layers in MCM-56. The bigger external surface area of the catalysts based on lamellar MFI compared to that of the MWW (Table 1) can be explained by the more developed interlayer voids in MFI, which also resulted in a bigger mesopore volume (V_{meso}) in these supports.

3.1.2.1. Catalysts under electron microscope – the metal NPs. Particle size distribution (PSD) from the TEM images of the catalysts reduced with H₂ (method described in section 2.3) confirmed the uniform size and distribution of Pd NPs on the layered supports (Fig. 3). The size of the majority of the Pd NPs in Pd/MFI_(lam,Si) and in Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) were about 6 and 4 nm, respectively (Fig. 3a and b). The dealumination resulted in a slight shift in the PSD for Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl) compared to Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si), with the majority of the NPs being smaller on the dealuminated support (about 2 nm, Fig. 3c). The PSD of the Pd NPs on the conventional MFI_(con) support had a maximum counts around 3 nm (Fig. 3d), making it possible to compare this reference 3D zeolite with

Table 1Chemical composition and textural properties of Pd/MFI_(lam,Si), Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si), Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl), Pd/MFI_(con), Pd/MCM-56, Pd/MCM-22, and commercial Pd/C_(com).

Catalyst	Si/Al, ICP-MS	Pd wt.%, theoretical	100*Pd/(Si + Al + Pd), ICP-MS	S _{BET} (m ² /g)	S _{ext.} (m ² /g)	V _{mic.} (cm ³ /g)	V _{meso.} (cm ³ /g)
Pd/MFI _(lam,Si)	∞	1 %	1 %	498	220	0.12	0.50
Pd/MFI _(lam,Al-Si)	22	1 %	1 %	443	251	0.08	0.31
Pd/MFI _(lam,deAl)	30	1 %	1 %	444	247	0.08	0.32
Pd/MFI _(con)	16	1 %	1 %	415	48	0.15	0.07
Pd/MCM-56	9	1 %	1 %	417	118	0.12	0.25
Pd/MCM-22	13	1 %	1 %	556	93	0.19	0.18
Pd/C _(com)	–	1 %	–	576	97	0.19	0.08

the layered MFI supports. The majority of the Pd NPs had a diameter of around 4 nm in Pd/MCM-56 (Fig. 3e), which made it possible to correlate any differences in the catalytic performance of this catalyst with that of Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) to the difference in the topology (and morphology) of these materials. The majority of the NPs in Pd/MCM-22 (Fig. 3g) were about 2 nm, and in commercial Pd/C_(com) (Fig. 3h), most of them had a size below 2 nm.

To see the effect of an extra calcination step after loading of the Pd NPs and before reduction of the Pd-support catalyst, we first impregnated Pd NPs on the MCM-56 support, and then calcined this Pd-MCM-56 at 350 °C for 4 h. Afterwards, we reduced this material (as described previously in section 2.3) to obtain Pd/MCM-56. The PSD data for this Pd/MCM-56_(calcined+reduced) showed a wider distribution in the size of the NPs (Fig. 3f) compared to that of Pd/MCM-56 (only reduced, Fig. 3e). This indicates that the calcination after impregnation of the support had an adverse effect on PSD, probably due to sintering of some of the NPs at high temperature (350 °C), which created NPs bigger than 15 nm on the same support.

The Pd NPs were anchored in between the lamella and on the external surface of the supports (Fig. 4, Right). The size of the majority of the Pd NPs on our designed Pd/support catalysts was in the range of 2–6 nm, which is the optimum range for the size of Pd NPs in the majority of hydrogenation reactions described up to now [25]. This means that the difference in the catalytic performance among these Pd/support catalysts would be mainly due to the difference in the characteristics of the support and not from a significant difference in the size of the Pd NPs.

3.1.2.2. Catalysts under electron microscope – the supports. The micro-scale SEM images of the catalysts reduced with H₂ (method described in section 2.3) showed the surface morphology of the support crystals, and the TEM images enabled us to analyze the structure of the supports at nanoscale (Fig. 4). From the SEM images at microscale (Fig. 4, Left, a-c), the crystals of layered MFI supports formed non-rigid aggregates of irregular shapes, made up of loosely stacked polygonal plates with a smooth exterior surface [19]. On the other hand, in the MWW materials (Fig. 4, Left, e,f), the very thin flakes of MWW crystals were well visible on the microscale images. These thin flakes had a more packed morphology and made round-shaped aggregates in the case of MCM-56 [26].

The TEM images at 100 nm scale very well revealed the layered structure of the designed MFI and MWW supports (Fig. 4, Right). These images confirmed that the layered MFI had 2D lamella with uniform thickness <10 nm (Fig. 4, Right, a-c). These lamella were loosely stacked on each other with only partial condensation of the layers even after calcination (before Pd impregnation) at high temperature [19]. This flake-like packing brought interparticle voids in between the 2D lamella, which was the reason for the appearance of the hysteresis in the adsorption isotherms discussed in section 3.1.2. The orientations of the thin and densely-packed MWW layers were more random (Fig. 4, Right, e,f) than in MFI. As we saw in section 3.1.2, this less orderly house-of-cards orientation of the MWW layers in MCM-56 caused a small deviation of the desorption isotherm from the adsorption isotherm and resulted in a hysteresis. We conclude that the electron microscopy images confirmed the layered structure of the supports, and they were

consistent with the data from PXRD patterns and the adsorption analysis.

3.1.3. Support functionality in the catalysts

In situ FTIR spectroscopy helped us to understand which type of acid sites (Brønsted, Lewis, or both) were present in the designed catalysts. Since pyridine was used as the probe molecule, the informative FTIR region for the appearance of the absorption bands due to pyridine interaction with the acid sites was 1400–1700 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 5, Top, Right). Al-free Pd/MFI_(lam,Si) showed low-intensity absorption bands of pyridine interacting with Si-OH groups at 1444 cm⁻¹, and with Lewis acid sites (LAS) at 1455 cm⁻¹ (concentration <0.01 mmol/g), which was removed already at 250 °C (Fig. S2). These results are in line with a lack of strong acid sites in Pd/MFI_(lam,Si) without Al in the framework positions.

Besides silanol groups on the external surface of crystals (Si-OH_{ext}) interacting with pyridine, Al-containing Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) and Pd/MCM-56 samples showed characteristic features of Brønsted acid sites (Py-B at 1546 cm⁻¹) and Lewis acid sites (Py-L at 1455 cm⁻¹, Fig. 5, Right) [27]. The intensities of respective Py-B and Py-L bands maintained or slightly decreased at 250 °C (Fig. S2). Compared to Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si), dealuminated Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl) showed decrease in Py-B band and an enhancement of Py-L and Py-SiOH bands, both external Si-OH_{ext} and internal Si-OH_{int} (Fig. 5). The decrease in Brønsted acidity is related to the removal Al atoms from the framework positions and thus the drop in the number of bridging Si-OH-Al groups.

This trend is consistent with the findings from ²⁷Al NMR spectra of dealuminated Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl), which showed an increased relative intensity of the signal at 0 ppm (assigned to extra-framework six-coordinated Al) compared to Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) (Fig. 5, Bottom). Further insights into the evolution of OH groups during dealumination were provided by ¹H MAS NMR (Fig. 5). The ¹H MAS NMR spectra of hydrated Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl) and Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) samples revealed two types of bridging Si-OH-Al groups: unperturbed groups at approximately 4 ppm and perturbed groups at around 6 ppm, influenced by hydrogen bonding [28]. This assignment was confirmed by 2D ¹H-²⁷Al NMR HETCOR spectra (Fig. 5, Bottom), which showed two cross-peaks at (δ_{1H}, δ_{27Al}) = (6.9 ppm, 54 ppm) and (3.1 ppm, 55 ppm).

Additionally, the ¹H MAS NMR spectra of both Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) and Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl) indicated isolated Si-OH groups at around 2 ppm and a signal near 1 ppm, typically associated with Al-OH groups. The assignment of the 1 ppm signal to Al-OH species was recently validated by theoretical calculations [28]. However, the inherently low sensitivity of 2D ¹H-²⁷Al NMR HETCOR within a reasonable experimental timeframe [29] prevented direct experimental confirmation of this signal in the studied samples.

Overall, FTIR and NMR spectroscopy revealed two key changes upon dealumination: (1) an increased fraction of Al-OH moieties and (2) the formation of additional non-acidic silanol groups (Fig. 5). These newly formed surface groups, along with the remaining acid sites, have the potential to influence the catalytic performance of Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl) through hydrogen bonding with thymol [17].

Fig. 3. Particle size distribution of (a) Pd/MFI_(lam,Si), (b) Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si), (c) Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl), (d) Pd/MFI_(con), (e) Pd/MCM-56, (f) Pd/MCM-56_(calclined+reduced), (g) Pd/MCM-22, and (h) Pd/C_(com).

3.2. Catalysis

3.2.1. Thymol hydrogenation reaction

Thymol hydrogenation was done in a batch reactor system under conditions described in section 2.3. Based on the H₂ TPR (temperature programmed reduction) profile, the catalysts were reduced at 350 °C before using in the reaction (Fig. S3). When Pd is used as the metal catalyst for hydrogenation of phenolic compounds like thymol, the ketone products are formed selectively [16,30–32]. Accordingly, the main

products from thymol hydrogenation on our designed catalysts were menthone (trans-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexanone) and isomenthone (cis-2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexanone). However, at high thymol conversions (at high menthone yields), deoxygenation of menthone provided a mixture of two menthane isomers (cis- and trans-p-menthane).

The yield of the menthane isomers increased even after full thymol conversion, indicating that deoxygenation of menthone was not competing with the aromatic ring hydrogenation, but it was a

Fig. 4. SEM (Left) and TEM images (Right) of the catalysts for (a) Pd/MFI_(lam, Si), (b) Pd/MFI_(lam, Al-Si), (c) Pd/MFI_(lam, deAl), (d) Pd/MFI_(con), (e) Pd/MCM-56, and (f) Pd/MCM-22.

subsequent reaction. This deoxygenation reaction can proceed through a sequential hydrogenation of the carbonyl group of menthone on Pd sites to give menthol, its dehydration on the acid sites, and further saturation of C=C bond on Pd sites to give menthane, as it was described for compounds containing similar functional groups [33].

A simplified reaction scheme is given in Fig. 6. For the purpose of our study, which was to correlate the acidic and topological properties of the support to the catalytic performance, we compared thymol conversion as the most important factor. In addition, the data regarding products' yield and distribution are also included for completeness. A blank experiment (without a catalyst) under the reaction conditions (150 °C and 20 bars hydrogen) showed less than 1 % thymol conversion over 5 h, which confirmed that the reaction needed a catalyst to provide an alternative pathway with lower activation energy.

3.2.2. Pairwise comparison between the catalysts

The conversion (X%) of thymol was different as a result of the distinctive key properties of the supports in the catalysts (Fig. 7). The fundamental difference in the acidity between purely siliceous and aluminosilicate MFIs (Fig. S2) caused a difference in the catalytic performance of Pd/MFI_(lam, Si) and Pd/MFI_(lam, Al-Si). Thymol conversion was higher on Pd/MFI_(lam, Al-Si) than on its siliceous non-acidic counterpart over 5 h of reaction time (Fig. 7a). This difference was only about 5 % at 1 h, but then increased to 25 % at 5 h. The support in both of these catalysts had the MFI topology, and the Pd NPs were homogeneously dispersed on both supports (Figs. 3 and 4, Right, a,b). Thus, the difference in the catalytic results of these two catalysts originated only from the difference in the acidity of their supports. Aluminosilicate MFI is acidic ($C_{\text{tot.}} = 0.18 \text{ mmol/g}$, Fig. S2), but MFI_(lam, Si) is not ($C_{\text{tot.}} < 0.02 \text{ mmol/g}$). As a result, the interaction of thymol with the surface of MFI_(lam, Al-Si) support was stronger than with MFI_(lam, Si).

The important role of the support in adsorbing the phenolic reactant and increasing its conversion has been investigated in similar studies, where the authors observed a direct correlation between the support-reactant interactions and the catalytic conversion, or where they found a significant increase in phenol conversion when the aluminosilicate analogue of a siliceous support was used [8,16,17]. Similarly, the better interaction of thymol molecules with the aluminosilicate MFI support resulted in its adsorption near Pd sites, where hydrogen atoms were activated, and this increased the conversion. Although the acidity of the support was a favorable factor, Pd/MFI_(lam, Al-Si) was still unable to convert more than 47 % of thymol in 5 h.

In the next pair of catalysts with the same support topology but different concentrations of acid sites and surface deficiencies, a significant difference between the results for Pd/MFI_(lam, Al-Si) and Pd/MFI_(lam, deAl) was noted. (Fig. 7b). The increase in total number of sites behaving as acid centers (see discussion in section 3.1.3 and Fig. S2) and the generation of extra silanol groups on the surface, as a result of dealumination of MFI_(lam, Al-Si), effectively enhanced the catalytic output. Over Pd/MFI_(lam, deAl), the reaction started at a fast pace to convert half of the initial amount of thymol in 1 h, and then continued to almost fully transform thymol to products in 3 h ($X = 98 \%$). Thymol conversion was 50 % higher on Pd/MFI_(lam, deAl) than on its aluminosilicate analogue after 5 h.

Pd/MFI_(lam, Al-Si) and Pd/MFI_(lam, deAl) both have acidic supports of the same MFI topology with uniformly dispersed Pd NPs (Figs. 3 and 4, Right, b,c). The differences between these two supports are the distribution of weak and strong acid sites as well as the defects created by dealumination of the zeolitic support. Furthermore, this dealumination treatment seems to have assisted with the incorporation of smaller Pd NPs (Fig. 3c). The higher conversion of thymol with dealuminated support can be a result of better interactions between thymol molecules and all the mentioned active centers including silanol groups through hydrogen bonding of thymol to these sites [8]. So, Pd/MFI_(lam, deAl) owes its superior activity not solely to being acidic, but also to its ability of keeping better interaction with thymol.

Fig. 5. (Top) FTIR spectra of (a) Pd/MFI_(lam,Si), (b) Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si), (c) Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl), and (d) Pd/MCM-56 in (Left) OH vibration region before pyridine adsorption and (Right) pyridine ring vibration region after pyridine ad-/desorption at 150 °C; (Bottom) ²⁷Al, ¹H and ¹H-²⁷Al HETCOR MAS NMR spectra of Pd-loaded MFI_(Al-Si), MFI_(deAl), and MCM-56.

Fig. 6. Reaction scheme of thymol hydrogenation in the presence of Pd-supported catalysts.

Next, we compare the catalytic results of Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) with those of Pd NPs supported on conventional aluminosilicate MFI_(con) (Fig. 7c). Thymol conversion profile over the reaction time was similar for both catalysts. If we compare the properties of these two catalysts (Table 1 and Fig. 3b, d), we see that both supports are aluminosilicate and acidic (Si/Al = 22 for Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) and 16 for Pd/MFI_(con)), and the majority of Pd NPs on these supports have around 3–4 nm diameter. From the similar and quite moderate catalytic output of the Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) and Pd/MFI_(con), in contrast to the optimized catalytic behavior of Pd/MFI_(lam,deAl), it is confirmed that the well accessible surface acid sites of the support in the form of defects and silanols are an important driving force for high thymol conversion.

The next pair for comparison is two catalysts with different topologies of the acidic support (Fig. 7d). Thymol conversion was higher on Pd/MCM-56 than on Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si). Over Pd/MCM-56, the conversion of thymol reached 40 % at 1 h, followed by 98 % at 3 h. The superior catalytic performance of Pd/MCM-56 compared to Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si) stemmed from the topology of its respective support (both supports were highly acidic, Fig. S2). MCM-56 has 12-ring cups on the exterior surface of its 2D layers, which probably acted as extra adsorption sites or extra

reaction space to accommodate thymol near Pd sites. In addition, MCM-56 has the house-of-cards morphology of the layers, while the lamella in MFI are more orderly packed on each other (Fig. 4, Right, e,b). The accessibility to the Pd NPs was more likely easier in the case of the MWW support. Pd/MCM-22 catalyst showed high thymol conversion, comparable to that of Pd/MCM-56 (Fig. 7e), because MCM-22 support also has the same MWW topology with well accessible 12-ring cups at slightly lower external surface but higher S_{BET} (Table 1).

To verify our conclusions from the effect of the support on the outcome of thymol hydrogenation reaction, we performed the reaction over commercial Pd/C(com) catalyst with 1 wt% Pd loading, and we compared the results with those of our designed catalysts (Fig. S4). The Pd/C(com) was practically inactive in thymol hydrogenation, probably as a consequence of the non-acidic nature of the support, which was unable to effectively engage thymol for reaction.

The product distribution over the catalysts at 3 h contact time and under the same reaction conditions were compared (Fig. 8). As mentioned before, two pairs of isomers were synthesized from thymol hydrogenation reaction over Pd-catalysts: menthone/isomenthone and trans-/cis-p-menthane. The p-menthane isomers were not detected by

Fig. 7. Pairwise comparison of catalysts; reaction conditions: 150 °C, 20 bars hydrogen, and 100 mg catalyst.

GC-FID when thymol conversion was below 35 %, which means in case of Pd/MFI(lam,Si) and Pd/MFI(lam,Al-Si). However, as thymol conversion increased, p-menthane isomers appeared in a small quantity to make up a maximum of 21 % of the products pool when using Pd/MCM-22.

Another interesting observation from the product distribution data is the difference in menthone/isomenthone ratio over the catalysts (Fig. 8). While with the acidic supports the yield of menthone was around 1.7 times bigger than the yield of isomenthone, the yield of menthone was actually much smaller in the case of non-acidic support. Due to restricted spatial configuration, isomenthone is less stable than menthone. So, a ratio of menthone/isomenthone >1 is expected at equilibrium. However, the opposite distribution of the menthone isomers over Pd/MFI(lam,Si) can be an indication of the low rate of reaction over this catalyst not reaching equilibrium.

3.2.3. Effect of reaction conditions

To understand the effect of the temperature, hydrogen pressure, and

the amount of the catalyst on thymol conversion, we performed the hydrogenation reaction under a set of various conditions using the Pd/MCM-56 catalyst (Fig. 9). The decrease or increase in thymol conversion was in accordance with the basic kinetics of chemical reactions. For instance, the highest conversions of thymol at the beginning of the reaction belonged to the experiment at the highest temperature (Fig. 9a) or the experiment at highest hydrogen pressure (Fig. 9b).

A similar trend for an increase in the conversion with an increase in the temperature has been observed for hydrogenation of other phenolic compounds [34]. Moreover, it has been observed in similar studies that the rate of hydrogenation of aromatic compounds can depend on hydrogen concentration (or pressure), with the order of reaction rate to hydrogen being difficult to generalize [35].

Thymol conversion decreased by decreasing the amount of the catalyst (Fig. 9c) indicating a lack of active sites to suffice the turnover of the reactants under these conditions. So, all these parameters were influential on thymol conversion. However, their influence became more pronounced when they passed some specific threshold (for

Fig. 8. Products distribution; reaction conditions: 3 h contact time, 150 °C, 20 bars hydrogen, and 100 mg catalyst.

instance 125 °C or 50 mg of catalyst, under the reaction conditions used). Thus, it is important to optimize the conditions for a similar reaction of interest.

Increasing the temperature increased the total yield of the products, but it had the most noticeable effect on transforming menthone isomers to p-menthanes (Fig. 10a). Even though the yield of menthone increased from 12 % to 43 % and to 56 % when the reaction temperature was increased from 100 to 125 and 150 °C, further increasing the temperature to 175 °C had an adverse effect on menthone's yield and decreased it to 37 %. A similar trend was observed for the yield of isomenthone: an increase in its yield from 12 % to 28 % and 33 % by an increase in the temperature from 100 to 125 and 150 °C followed by a decrease to 21 % at 175 °C. Thus, increasing the temperature to 175 °C seems to have had

facilitated the deoxygenation of menthone isomers to give p-menthane isomers.

Increasing the pressure from 10 to 20 bars of hydrogen increased the yield of menthone isomers by about 10 % for each (from 47 % to 56 % for menthone and from 23 % to 33 % for isomenthone; Fig. 10b). However, by a further increase to 50 bars, the yield of menthone remained the same and that of isomenthone decreased to 28 %. Increasing the pressure was generally favorable for the yield of p-menthane isomers, which suggests that deoxygenation occurs at harsher conditions of pressure (and temperature as we saw earlier).

Increasing the amount of the catalyst resulted in a higher yield for all the products (Fig. 10c). The yield of menthone increased from 23 % to 56 % and the yield of isomenthone increased from 13 % to 33 % as a result of more available active sites provided by 100 mg of Pd/MCM-56 compared to 25 mg. These abundant active sites also facilitated the transformation of menthone isomers to p-menthane isomers, providing 8 % of p-menthanes in the products pool.

3.2.4. Regeneration of Pd/MCM-56

Pd/MCM-56 was used in consecutive catalytic cycles to investigate the performance of the regenerated catalyst after multiple runs (Fig. 11). After each cycle, the catalyst was washed several times with the solvent (n-octane) and it was dried at room temperature overnight. Although Pd/MCM-56 showed optimum thymol conversion in the first catalytic run, thymol conversion dropped to 67 % and 46 % in the second and third cycles, respectively. The partial deactivation of the catalyst can be a result of its pore blockage with the products, which can be alleviated by a more elaborate regeneration treatment (drying at a slightly elevated temperature and re-reduction before use in the next cycle), or it can be due to the sintering of some of the Pd NPs under the reaction conditions, which can be further investigated by full characterization of the spent catalyst or via operando techniques.

4. Conclusions

The support did play a crucial role in thymol hydrogenation reaction. While Pd/MFI_(lam,Si) was almost inactive in the reaction (conversion below 25 %), introducing acidity in the same MFI topology enhanced the

Fig. 9. Effect of reaction conditions; thymol hydrogenation over Pd/MCM-56 at different (a) temperatures, (b) hydrogen pressures, and (c) catalyst amounts.

Fig. 10. Effect of reaction conditions on products distribution in thymol hydrogenation over Pd/MCM-56 at 3 h of reaction time at different (a) temperatures, (b) hydrogen pressures, and (c) catalyst amounts.

Fig. 11. Consecutive cycles of reaction with Pd/MCM-56; reaction conditions: 3 h contact time, 150 °C, 20 bars hydrogen, and 100 mg catalyst.

catalytic output (conversion reaching 47 %) due to better support-thymol interactions. Furthermore, dealumination of the same MFI_(Al-Si) layers enriched the surface of the support with functional groups, to which thymol had high affinity resulting in almost full conversion.

Other than the acidity of the support, its topology also significantly affected the catalytic data. The performance of Pd/MCM-56 was superior compared to Pd/MFI_(lam,Al-Si), because the cups on the exterior surface of MWW layers provided extra functionality and reaction space, which were easily accessible to thymol through the MWW topology. These findings about the correlation of particular properties of the support with conversion and reaction output can be used for hydrogenation reactions involving other phenolic compounds.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fateme Poorsharbat Ghavi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Martin Kubů:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Oleg Petrov:** Formal analysis, Investigation. **Monika Remzová:** Formal analysis, Investigation. **Subhajyoti Samanta:** Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jan Prech:** Supervision, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maksym Opanasenko:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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